

Energy Modeling of a Self-Sustainable Base Station

Juho Markkula

University of Oulu, Finland

Email: juho.markkula@oulu.fi

Sanna Tuomela

University of Oulu, Finland

Email: sanna.tuomela@oulu.fi

Hamid Malik

University of Oulu, Finland

Email: hamid.malik@oulu.fi

Antti Pauanne

University of Oulu, Finland

Email: antti.pauanne@oulu.fi

Abstract—Electrical grid may not be available for providing power for cellular networks in remote locations such as forests and mountains. However, having connectivity in this kind of wilderness areas would be beneficial, for example, for being able to connect to the Internet and having voice calls. Alternatively, renewable energy sources such as wind, solar, and hydrogen could be utilized to power up the base station. This paper studies with Matlab simulations the energy modeling of a self-sustainable base station. Two different selections of equipment for renewable energy sources to provide sufficient energy for an open radio access network (O-RAN) base station for the whole year with extremely varying weather conditions in Oulu, Northern Finland were evaluated.

I. INTRODUCTION

Sustainability is a key driver for 6G research and development [1], [2], and energy consumption is one of the main factors for sustainable future telecommunication networks [3]. The changing geopolitical situation, climate change and rapid digitalization set new requirements for telecommunication networks' reliable, resilient and sustainable operations in all conditions. This calls for effort from two complementary aspects: 1) energy efficiency to reduce telecommunication network energy consumption on one hand and 2) energy self-sustainability to open up new energy supplies for telecommunication network operations. Energy efficiency of 5G/6G networks has been widely studied in several research projects [4] but it is necessary to extend the focus beyond analyzing energy consumption, encompassing the entire lifecycle from energy generation to consumption. So far, the sustainable and resilient energy supply for telecommunication networks has gained less attention and has mostly focused on energy-harvesting [5], a method to capturing small amounts of energy from the environment to power a device.

As discussed in [6], Arctic and other remote environments present significant challenges for communication connectivity. Their work demonstrates that wireless technologies can be adapted to operate under such extreme conditions; however, the absence of supporting infrastructure, most notably a reliable power grid, necessitates the deployment of sustainable and self-sufficient energy solutions. The use of renewable energy sources (RES) to power base stations in harsh environments has been investigated in prior studies [7], [8], including radio access networks (RANs) [9], and evaluated through simulation-based analyses under various scenarios [10], [11], [12]. The photovoltaic (PV) grid hybrid and battery backup system is the most used and economical solution for powering mobile networks as discussed in [10]. Such hybrid systems not only supports the green energy adoption in developing countries but also enable sustainable expansion of cellular networks. In the proposed solution [10], PV battery grid system, solar

power supplies about 77% of the total energy, while the grid providing the remaining 23%. When a diesel generator is included, solar energy still accounts for 75% of the total supply, the grid provides 23%, and the generator contributes only 2%. In [11], the authors propose a use case where 5G base stations and electric two wheelers (E2Ws) share the same RES through battery swapping system. The approach utilizes periods of high renewable availability for charging batteries, thus reducing operational costs and improving RES utilization for both mobile networks and E2W charging stations. In [12], a battery backup based base station model powered by solar and wind energy is developed, and a charge/discharge control strategy along with economic modeling is deployed to demonstrate energy efficient, cost effective, and sustainable operation of cellular networks with reduced reliance on the power grid. Nevertheless, much of the existing literature focuses on regions with year-round solar availability or considers highly constrained and location-specific simulation scenarios. In contrast, this paper presents a holistic simulation framework that accounts for a diverse range of RES configurations and is adaptable to multiple geographic locations and environmental conditions.

In this article, we focus on the less studied energy supply side for the telecommunication networks and examine the energy balance of an off-grid, entirely renewable energy (RE) powered 5G open RAN (O-RAN) base-station radio unit that may be placed in remote, harsh conditions and should provide service for users in all weather, temperature and usage conditions. The energy consumption of all parts and functions of the self-sustainable base station solution has been estimated at different temperatures, and RE resources and battery have been selected so that the base-station operates all year round in harsh Arctic conditions without any grid power supply. The developed simulator provides accurate modeling of RE availability for self-sustainable cellular network in off-grid remote environments using site-specific University of Oulu, Technical Research Centre of Finland (VTT) [13], and Finnish Meteorological Institute (FMI) [14] measurements for estimating hourly values of wind speed, temperature, and solar PV output at specified geographical coordinates and panel installation angles. The simulator is a preparation for the Finnish pilot in the EU Horizon Europe SNS-JU 6G-VERSUS project. The proposed simulation model is adaptable and scalable to any kind of geographic conditions and for different RE asset compositions.

The paper is organized as follows. In Section II the Matlab simulator for self-sustainable base station is described. Section III presents two simulations cases with different equipment selections for renewable energy sources. The simulation results are presented in Section IV and Section V concludes the paper.

Fig. 1. Simplified picture of the self-sustainable base station architecture.

II. SIMULATOR FOR A SELF-SUSTAINABLE BASE STATION

The modeling of a self-sustainable base station requires the calculation of how much energy is required by the remote unit equipment: radio unit, the microwave link as backhaul, the heating, and other electrical components. The total energy production must be matched with the consumption of the remote unit of the base station. Thus, there should be sufficient energy to run the base station throughout the year, while avoiding excess renewable energy sources such as solar panels and batteries in order to reduce costs.

The Matlab simulator for energy modeling of self-sustainable base station was developed. Figure 1 presents the simplified picture of the self-sustainable base station architecture. Solely the open radio unit (O-RU) of O-RAN base station was planned to be placed in the location without an access to the electrical grid: remote unit powered by RES utilizing 5G O-RAN enabled intelligent energy control system. The O-RU can be connected to other parts of the base station in the network side: open centralized unit (O-CU), open distributed unit (O-DU), and 5G standalone (5G SA) core, via the microwave transceiver (TRX). The main purpose of this simulator was to obtain information for selecting suitable RES devices for a real-life testbed, aimed at covering the energy consumption of remote unit equipment. Thus, the purpose was to study for example how many solar panels, what kind of wind turbine, what capacity of battery bank, and how much hydrogen is necessary to cover up the energy usage of the remote unit for entire annual year. The simulator modeled the energy consumption of different equipment in the remote unit and the energy production of applied RES devices. Simulations are performed by considering varying weather conditions during specific annual year and the energy consumption and production are hourly evaluated. Starting month for the simulations can be freely selected. Multiple different locations are available to be selected for simulation runs having effect on hourly wind speeds, solar radiation, and temperature values.

The power consumption of the following remote unit equipment were considered: O-RU (62-68 W), microwave TRX (51 W), wired Ethernet router (2.2 W), mini-PC that runs Linux (7 W), communication and control hub of the energy system (2.8 W), two pieces of DC power distribution and protection modules (2.4 W), two pieces of DC converters

(6.9 W), solar controller (1 W), wind charge controller (3 W), battery controller (0.6 W), and the stand by power of hydrogen power plant (4.4 W). Note that the hourly power consumption of the O-RU depends on the given parameter for communication to idle ratio in percentages (0 - 100%): power consumption for each second is modeled as 62 W when idle and 68 W during communication with a 100 MHz bandwidth and a 4x4 multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) antenna configuration.

In addition, the energy consumption required for heating two storage boxes is calculated analytically using Fourier's law of heat conduction [15] during the simulation, based on the given simulator parameters (Table I). The size of the storing box for the batteries and electrical devices is calculated by the simulator by considering the number and size of the selected batteries. Also, the selected minimum temperatures for the boxes, the thicknesses and material for the insulation on the walls of the boxes can be given as input parameters. In addition, varying outside temperature is considered depending on the selected remote unit location. Furthermore, an additional ventilation hole in the hydrogen fuel cell generator storage box, designed to release hydrogen in the event of a leak, is analytically accounted when estimating the power consumption associated with warm air escaping and cold air entering through the opening. The ventilation for the storage boxes used during warm time periods is also planned to be installed in the real-life testbed. However, the energy consumption caused by the ventilation is not considered in the simulator because during the warm time periods there is plenty of solar power available.

The energy production of the following RES devices is modeled for the simulator: multiple wind power plants, different types and numbers of solar panels and batteries, and various models of hydrogen fuel cell generators. For batteries, the starting charge (5% - 100%) and the number of completed charge-discharge cycles (0, 2500, 3000, or 5000) can be selected to determine the maximum battery charge (100%, 80%, 70%, or 50%, respectively).

The simulator also accounts for various electrical losses that occur during energy storage and conversion to different forms, such as voltage levels. Battery round trip efficiency (92%) defines how much of stored energy can be consumed by the electrical devices. Thus, approximately 8% of the energy is lost when the electricity is charged and discharged from the batteries. The hydrogen fuel cell output must be converted from 24 V DC to 48 V DC with an efficiency of 89%. In addition, voltage level conversion from 48 V DC to 24 V DC with an efficiency of 93% is required to supply power from the batteries to the Ethernet router and to charge the internal battery of the hydrogen fuel cell. In addition, the efficiency of heating elements of battery and hydrogen fuel cell boxes are considered to be 90%.

III. SIMULATION CASES

Multiple simulation cases with different input parameter selections were performed using the Matlab simulator for energy modeling of self-sustainable base station to select two simulation cases for this article (Table I). These two simulation cases 1 and 2 both provided sufficient energy

production for the base station system for the whole year 2024 at Linnanmaa, Oulu, Finland. The input parameter selection of the simulation case 1 resulted sufficient energy production without any hydrogen usage. The simulation case 2 has the same input parameter selection than the case 1 but contains one battery less in the battery bank: 17 (87 kWh) versus 18 (92 kWh) batteries. The case 2 required also some hydrogen energy production that needs to be minimized due to the high cost and limited amount of hydrogen in the cylinder (e.g., 50 liters). The hydrogen fuel cell generator is utilized as the last energy source to power up the base station equipment in case that the other RES (solar and wind) are not able to provide sufficient energy during the specific hour and the batteries have low energy: minimum allowed battery charge is 10%.

Months of the year 2024 were shifted to start from May because it was considered as a time for the maintenance visit at the self-sustainable base station site, and also the most energy challenging time period (winter) was needed to be simulated from beginning to end. Communication to idle ratio for the O-RU was selected to be 25% considering a remote location with relatively low traffic and corresponding on average to hourly energy consumption of 63.5 Wh. Estimated electricity consumption in addition to powering the O-RU and storage box heating was about 81.3 W for the electrical devices introduced in the previous section. The number of solar panels (8) and the wind power plant size and model were selected also by considering the installing location on the roof of the University of Oulu. A powerful vertical wind turbine (5 kW) still suitable for the installation location was selected to provide as much as possible energy during the wintertime when there is extremely low solar power available.

The model of batteries was selected to provide 48 V DC current supported by most of the devices in the testbed. The number of batteries (18) for the case 1 was selected sufficiently high for not to require any hydrogen power generation to electrify the remote unit equipment. In the case 2, the number of batteries was reduced by one (17) to demonstrate also the hydrogen energy production. Batteries were considered new with 80% starting charge. Minimum temperature maintained in the battery box was selected to be 15 °C still providing the maximum capacity for the batteries. Hydrogen fuel cell model, PowerUP 400, was selected to provide sufficient electrical power for the remote unit and also to offer sufficient communication and control capabilities to be able to power on and off the device when necessary. Minimum temperature maintained in the hydrogen fuel cell box was selected to be 5 °C being clearly above the minimum use temperature (−5 °C). Insulation foam material for the walls of the boxes was considered as polyurethane providing good heat insulation capability with 13 cm thickness. The heating of storage box for the battery bank and electrical devices consumed energy hourly from 0 to 79.5 Wh, and the heating of storage box for the hydrogen fuel cell generator consumed energy hourly from 0 to 10.5 Wh. The size of the storage box for the battery bank and electrical devices was the same in the both simulation cases for 17 and 18 batteries. The size was calculated in the simulator by placing the batteries on the same level and two batteries side by side, also leaving 2 cm free space on the sides and 10 cm free space on above of each battery. The height of the box was doubled to consider room in the box also for the electrical devices in addition to batteries. Thus, the storage

TABLE I. INPUT PARAMETER SELECTIONS FOR THE SIMULATION CASES 1 AND 2

Input parameter	Case 1	Case 2
Starting month		May
Communication to idle ratio for O-RU		25%
Power consumption in addition to O-RU and heating		81.3 W
Number of solar panels		8
Solar panel model		Trina Vertex 415 W
Wind power plant model		SkyPower 5kW Vertical
Location of the remote unit		Linnanmaa, Oulu, Finland
Battery model		Victron LFP-51,2V/100Ah/5120Wh
Number of batteries in the battery bank	18 (92 kWh)	17 (87 kWh)
The age (cycle life) of the batteries		New (100% capacity)
Starting charge of the batteries		80%
Minimum temperature maintained in the battery box		15 °C
Thickness of the insulation for the battery box		13 cm
Hydrogen fuel cell model		PowerUP UP400 (400 W)
Min temperature maintained in the hydrogen cell box		5 °C
Thickness of the insulation for the hydrogen cell box		13 cm
Insulation foam material for the walls of the boxes		Polyurethane ($k: 0.026 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$)

Fig. 2. Cumulative energy for the simulation case 1 (18 batteries).

box dimensions were 67 cm in height, 135.6 cm in width, and 165.8 cm in depth, resulting in a total volume of approximately 1.5 m³. The storage box for the hydrogen fuel cell generator has a volume of approximately 0.05 m³ and includes a circular ventilation hole with a 2 cm diameter.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

Figures 2 and 3 present cumulative energy production, consumption, and status values from the beginning of May to the end of April during the year 2024 for the simulation case 1 (18 batteries) and case 2 (17 batteries), respectively. Total energy production contains a sum of solar, wind, and hydrogen energy production. Total energy consumption contains the consumption sum of all remote unit equipment such as O-RU, microwave TRX, storage box heating, and other necessary electrical devices presented in Section II. Total energy status shows how much unnecessary energy has been produced during the year, i.e., the energy that is produced but not consumed by the remote unit of self-sustainable base station.

Figures 2 and 3 illustrate that the yearly total energy production is about 3345 kWh and 3347 kWh in the simulation cases 1 and 2, respectively. It consists of solar energy production of 2288 kWh and wind energy production of 1057 kWh. Figure 4 illustrates that no hydrogen energy production was needed in the simulation case 1 because there were sufficient solar and wind energy production and battery capacity to provide energy for the remote unit equipment during the whole year. Hourly battery energy status curve shows that the maximum capacity of the battery bank (18

Fig. 3. Cumulative energy for the simulation case 2 (17 batteries).

Fig. 4. Battery energy status and hydrogen energy production for the simulation case 1 (18 batteries).

batteries) is 92.2 kWh. The minimum charge of batteries was 11.4 kWh being 12.4% of the maximum capacity. Thus, there were always at minimum 2.4% of battery capacity available while the minimum allowed charge for the batteries was 10%. Figures 2 and 3 show that there were 2 kWh higher total energy production in the simulation case 2 than in case 1 because having 1 battery less caused the need for hydrogen energy production. The hydrogen energy production in the simulation case 2 presented in Figure 5 shows that in late January 2.2 kWh of hydrogen energy is consumed corresponding approximately to hydrogen consumption of 5.5 liters. Hourly battery energy status curve shows that the maximum capacity of the battery bank (17 batteries) is 87.0 kWh, and the minimum charge of batteries was 8.7 kWh being 10% of the maximum charge. Thus, to avoid shutting down the base station it is necessary to utilize hydrogen fuel cell for producing energy when there is only 10% of battery charge left and no sufficient wind and solar power available.

The solar energy production curve illustrates that in Oulu, Northern Finland, there is not much solar light available during the winter months. For example, during the darkest winter month, December, only 1 kWh of solar energy was generated. The highest solar energy production (447 kWh) occurred on May. For the simulation cases of this article, actual measured values of solar energy production on the roof of the University of Oulu throughout the entire year 2024 were utilized by scaling the values to consider the given input parameters: the

Fig. 5. Battery energy status and hydrogen energy production for the simulation case 2 (17 batteries).

number of solar panels and the selected solar panel model that was more effective than the old model in use.

Based on the simulation results, the wind power plant is capable of providing energy consistently throughout the year. Wind energy production is higher in the winter months than in the summer, which is the opposite pattern observed for solar energy production. For example, Figures 2 and 3 show that 153 kWh of wind energy was produced during December being the month with the highest amount of produced wind energy due to the highest monthly average wind speed of 2.7 m/s. The lowest wind energy production (38 kWh) was in June with the lowest monthly average wind speed of 1.8 m/s. The average wind speed of July (1.9 m/s) was slightly higher than the wind speed of June. Thus, slightly more wind energy (by 4 kWh) was produced in July (31 days) than in June (30 days), also because July is a longer month. The wind speed values utilized in these simulation cases were measured at VTT Oulu located a few hundred meters from the University of Oulu premises: the average wind speed for the year, calculated from hourly measurements, was relatively low about 2.2 m/s on the roof of a few-story building [13]. The amount of produced wind energy was hourly calculated by using the measured wind speed values and the power curves obtained in laboratory environment by the wind turbine manufacturer. In addition, simulations considered 20% smaller wind energy production than the power curve indicated for providing more realistic results. The wind turbine started to produce energy at wind speeds above 2 m/s.

Yearly total energy consumption in the simulation case 1 (Figure 2) and case 2 (Figure 3) was 1463 kWh. The energy consumption of the remote unit equipment remained relatively consistent throughout the year, except for the heating of storage boxes, which consumed a significant amount of energy during the winter months due to low temperatures, unlike in the summer when heating was unnecessary. The highest total energy consumption (150 kWh) occurred in January being the coldest month of the year (average temperature: -11.7°C). The lowest total energy consumption (105 kWh) was on June with the average temperature of 18.9°C . The average temperature of July (19.9°C) was slightly higher than the temperature of June. However, total energy consumption in July was slightly higher (by 3 kWh) than in June, due to July having more days.

Total energy status in Figures 2 and 3 shows that 1832 kWh and 1834 kWh of unnecessary energy have been produced during the year in the simulation cases 1 and 2, respectively. The simulation case 2 produced approximately 2 kWh more energy due to the use of hydrogen fuel cell that was not needed to be utilized in the simulation case 1. Yearly total energy production subtracted with the total energy consumption in the simulation cases 1 and 2 were 1882 kWh and 1884 kWh, respectively. Thus, the difference between production and consumption is slightly higher than the total energy status value, by 50 kWh. It indicates that 50 kWh corresponds to the energy lost because of the 92% round-trip efficiency for using the batteries for storing the excess wind and solar energy and using this energy when hourly wind and solar energy does not cover the hourly total energy consumption of the remote unit equipment. Total energy status curves also illustrate that all the produced energy is consumed from the December to the middle of February because the curves stay constant at the 1520 kWh level. Thus, the reason why the total energy status curves show remarkable amount of unnecessary energy production is that the RES capacity is planned to cover the cold and dark winter months from November to March in the Northern Finland, and during the other months the energy production is remarkable higher than the consumption.

V. CONCLUSION

The simulation results demonstrate that the proposed simulator can provide valuable information for selecting suitable RES equipment, including the number of solar panels, type of wind turbine, battery bank capacity, and the amount of hydrogen required to cover the energy demand of a self-sustainable base station throughout the entire year. These results will be used to guide the selection of RES equipment for a real-life testbed to be constructed on the roof of the University of Oulu, Finland.

Two simulation cases with different battery bank capacities were investigated. Hydrogen energy generation was required when the battery capacity was smaller. Hydrogen usage should be minimized, as it is an expensive and limited resource due to the relatively small cylinder size, and should only serve as a last-resort energy source. The wind power plant appears to be the most suitable renewable energy source in Northern Finland, providing relatively consistent energy during long periods with little or no sunlight. Therefore, the optimal location for a self-sustainable base station in Northern Finland would be an open area or a hill with relatively high wind conditions.

Simulation of the energy self-sustainable base station provides a research platform for further research as well as a business decision tool. It can be leveraged and adapted to evaluate and compare technologies, for example renewable energy mixes for powering telecommunication networks or selected components, to apply energy management algorithms for various conditions, to assess trade-offs between quality of service, coverage, and energy consumption, to identify optimal locations for self-sustainable sites, to measure energy assets to supply power in selected conditions and to assess energy shortfall probabilities. The simulation helps to improve the energy models to power mobile networks with renewable energy, to assess investment and operating costs for the energy self-sustainable mobile network operations, and to improve

energy efficiency and reduce CO₂ emissions of mobile network services to further advance sustainability of next generation mobile networks.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

6G-VERSUS project has received funding from the Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU) under the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101192633.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Matinmikko-Blue *et al.*, "White paper on 6G drivers and the UN SDGs," 6G Research Visions, no. 2, Univ. of Oulu, Oulu, Finland, 2020. [Online]. Available: <http://urn.fi/urn:isbn:9789526226699>
- [2] I. Patsouras *et al.*, "6G KVis – SNS projects initial survey results 2025," Zenodo, White Paper, 2025. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.15220946
- [3] A. Hecker *et al.*, "Sustainability of 6G: Ways to reduce energy consumption," Zenodo, White Paper, 2024. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13986789
- [4] I. Mesogiti *et al.*, "6G KPIs—Definitions and target values," Zenodo, White Paper, 2025. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.15011631
- [5] O. López *et al.*, "Zero-energy devices for 6G: Technical enablers at a glance," *IEEE Internet of Things Mag.*, vol. 8, no. 3, pp. 14–22, May 2025, doi: 10.1109/IOTM.001.2400138.
- [6] P. Pirinen, H. Saarnisaari, J. van de Beek, M. Matinmikko-Blue, R. Nilsson, and M. Latva-aho, "Wireless Connectivity for Remote and Arctic Areas – Food for Thought," in *Proc. 16th Int. Symp. Wireless Communication Systems (ISWCS)*, Oulu, Finland, Sept. 2019, pp. 43–47, doi: 10.1109/ISWCS.2019.8877348.
- [7] B. M. Makhkamdjanov, "Technological Model of the Independent Power Supply with Converters of Renewable Energy for Base Station of Mobile Communication," in *Proc. 2nd IEEE/IFIP Int. Conf. Central Asia on Internet (CANET)*, Tashkent, Uzbekistan, 2006, pp. 1–4, doi: 10.1109/CANET.2006.279237.
- [8] Y. M. Khalifa, S. M. Syour, and F. S. Alarqt, "Optimal Design of a Hybrid Renewable Energy System Powering Mobile Radio Base Station in Libya," in *Proc. IEEE 1st Int. Maghreb Meeting Conf. Sciences and Techniques of Automatic Control and Computer Engineering (MI-STA)*, Tripoli, Libya, 2021, pp. 423–429, doi: 10.1109/MI-STA52233.2021.9464498.
- [9] A. Ndikumana, K. K. Nguyen, and M. Cheriet, "Renewable Energy Powered and Open RAN-Based Architecture for 5G Fixed Wireless Access Provisioning in Rural Areas," *IEEE Trans. Green Commun. Netw.*, vol. 8, no. 3, pp. 994–1007, Sept. 2024, doi: 10.1109/TGCN.2024.3431989.
- [10] A. Kabir, E. J. Kitindi, Z. ul Abidin Jaffri, G. Rehman, F. B. Ubaid, and M. S. Iqbal, "Economic and sustainable power solution for remote cellular network sites through renewable energy," in *Proc. IEEE 2nd Int. Conf. Information Technology, Networking, Electronic and Automation Control (ITNEC)*, Chengdu, China, 2017, pp. 1067–1072, doi: 10.1109/ITNEC.2017.8284903.
- [11] X. Liu and Z. Bie, "Cooperative Planning of Distributed Renewable Energy Assisted 5G Base Station With Battery Swapping System," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 119353–119366, 2021, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3108041.
- [12] J. Bai, H. H. Goh, X. Liang, X. Xie, T. A. Kurniawan, and Y. Song, "Decarbonisation Pathways for Empowering Telecom Networks Using Renewable Energy," in *Proc. IEEE 7th Int. Electrical and Energy Conf. (CIEEC)*, Harbin, China, 2024, pp. 2616–2621, doi: 10.1109/CIEEC60922.2024.10583346.
- [13] Technical Research Centre of Finland (VTT), "Weather Statistics," [Online]. Available: <https://weather.willab.fi/stats.html>. Accessed: Feb. 6, 2026.
- [14] Finnish Meteorological Institute, "Download observations," [Online]. Available: <https://en.ilmatiiteenlaitos.fi/download-observations>. Accessed: Feb. 6, 2026.
- [15] F. P. Incropera, D. P. DeWitt, T. L. Bergman, and A. S. Lavine, *Fundamentals of Heat and Mass Transfer*, 8th ed. Hoboken, NJ, USA: John Wiley & Sons, 2018, pp. 1–45.